

Green Inhibitors for Corrosion of Metals: A Review

Devarayan Kesavan^{1,2*}, Mayakrishnan Gopiraman^{1,3}, Nagarajan Sulochana^{1**}

¹Department of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology, Tiruchirappalli-620 015, Tamil Nadu, India. ²Institute of High Polymer Research, ³Nano Fusion Technology Research Lab, Department of Bioscience and Textile Technology, Interdisciplinary Graduate School of Science and Technology, Shinshu University, Ueda, Nagano 386-8567, Japan.

Abstract

Corrosion is an unavoidable but a controllable process. Due to the issues of toxicity of substances like chromate inhibitors, there is an increasing interest in exploration and utilization of eco-friendly inhibitors, which are also known as green inhibitors. This review briefly discusses some of the interesting features of the green inhibitors reported during the last decade.

Correspondence:

** N. Sulochana, Department of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology, Tiruchirappalli-620 015, Tamil Nadu, India. Email n.sulocha@gmail.com

* D. Kesavan, Institute of High Polymer Research, Department of Bioscience and Textile Technology, Interdisciplinary Graduate School of Science and Technology, Shinshu University, Ueda, Nagano 386-8567, Japan. Email kesavannitt@gmail.com

Keywords Corrosion inhibition, Green inhibitors, Plant extracts, Amino acids, Polymers

Introduction

Metals are the pre-eminent important materials used in structural and decorative applications. The corrosion, deterioration or destruction of metals is an unavoidable but controllable process. The corrosion of metals has a significant impact on the development of a country, which can be compared to any natural disasters like earthquake, flood, etc. For example; the direct metallic corrosion cost in the US was estimated as approximately \$276 billion on an annual basis, which is several times greater than the normalized loss incurred due to the natural disasters (\$17 billion per annum). It was also suggested that about 25-30% of the annual corrosion costs could be saved by means of optimum corrosion management practices [1].

Several different methods can be employed to slow or prevent corrosion of metallic structures. The most commonly used methods are protective coatings on metals using organic molecules, plastics, polymers; and cathodic and/or anodic protection using organic or inorganic inhibitors. The initial report of corrosion inhibition by organic inhibitors is attributed to Speller [2], who examined the corrosion inhibition of scaled water pipes in HCl. Since then, many organic and inorganic compounds that are added to the corrosive fluids have been investigated for this purpose.

There are growing concerns about certain compounds like chromates as inhibitors for corrosion processes, mainly due to the issue of toxicity. Green inhibitors like natural products from plant extracts and substances from other renewable sources are of the interest of the researchers who are interested in “green chemistry” or “eco-friendly” technologies. The literature contains a number of references on green corrosion inhibitors. Rather than concentrate on the more historical work on green inhibitors added to the

corrosive fluids, this review concentrates on the advances made in the last ten years. However, in order to highlight the growing interest on “corrosion inhibition of mild steel in corrosive fluids”, the authors have performed a survey on the literature published during 1950-2010.

Table 1 Recent trends in publications related to corrosion inhibitors

Decades	Number of publications
1951-1960	29
1961-1970	1235
1971-1980	1711
1981-1990	2685
1991-2000	4819
2001-2010	9873

The number of articles published has been doubled during the last decade (2001-2010) compared to 1991-2000 (**Table 1**). The increasing number of publications clearly indicates the interest in exploring the new inhibitors for a variety of corrosive environments in order to control the corrosion of various metals. Although the number of investigations on corrosion inhibitors has dramatically increased, only 5% of the literature published during the last decade concerns green inhibitors.

While other reviews [3-7] deal with the mechanisms of corrosion inhibition, this review focuses primarily on the effectiveness of green inhibitors in corrosive fluids, which are mainly plant extracts. The significance of natural polymers like starch and cellulose derivatives against corrosion of metals is also discussed. The selectivity of green

inhibitors towards metals and the effect of aging are as well discussed.

Green inhibitors

An inhibitor is a substance (or a combination of substances) added in a very low concentration to treat the surface of a metal that is exposed to a corrosive environment that terminates or diminishes the corrosion of a metal. These are also known as site blocking elements, blocking species or adsorption site blockers, due to their adsorptive properties [8, 9]. The term “green inhibitor” or “eco-friendly inhibitor” refers to the substances that have biocompatibility in nature. The inhibitors like plant extracts presumably possess biocompatibility due to their biological origin. Similar to the general classification of “inhibitors”, “green inhibitors” can also be grouped into two categories, namely organic green inhibitors and inorganic green inhibitors.

Organic green inhibitors

The organic green inhibitors are the flavonoids, alkaloids and other natural products obtained from natural sources like plants [4]. It also includes synthetic compounds with negligible toxicity. Some of the notable developments on organic green inhibitors especially plant extracts are discussed here.

Plant extracts

The authors have so far investigated the application of plant extracts [10, 11], as well as other organic inhibitors [12-17] against corrosion of steel in acidic fluids. Loto had reported the application of the extract of *Mangifera indica* (Common name: mango, indigenous area: India and other tropical regions) leaves and bark for corrosion of mild steel in diluted sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) medium [18, 19]. The weight loss measurements and electrochemical impedance spectroscopic studies were used to determine the inhibition efficiency of the inhibitors. Though the extract of leaves and bark showed a significant effect on the corrosion rate separately, the combination of these two extracts exhibited rather higher efficiency.

The inhibitive effect of *Zenthoxylum alatum* (Winged Prickly Ash, East and South Asian Countries) fruit extract was reported for corrosion of mild steel in phosphoric acid medium at temperatures ranging from 50–80 °C [20]. The surface analysis using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) revealed the layer formation of the plant extract on the surface of mild steel. And the results were indicated the possible formation of iron phosphate that was catalyzed by the formation of the iron-plant extract organo-metallic complex.

Satapathy et al studied the methanol extract of *Justicia gendarussa* (Willow-leaved justicia, India, Indonesia) leaves for corrosion inhibition of mild steel in hydrochloric acid medium (HCl) [21]. The authors have made an attempt to characterize the organic compounds present in the methanol extract by means of gas chromatography- mass spectrometric technique. The results showed that the compounds present in the methanol extract were difficult to separate, since the

retention times of majority of the compounds were close to each other. The electron spectroscopy for chemical analysis and atomic force microscopy were employed to obtain the information about the film formation on the surface of the mild steel specimen.

The inhibitive action of leaves, seeds and a combination of leaves and seeds of *phyllanthus amarus* (Stonebreaker, India and other tropical regions) was reported by Okafor et al, for corrosion of mild steel in HCl and H_2SO_4 [22]. The half-life time of mild steel in the electrolyte solution containing the acid and the combined extract of leaves and seeds showed increased resistance for the mild steel towards both the corrosive environments. The positive values of heat of adsorption revealed the chemical adsorption of the inhibitors on the mild steel surface, which was well supported by adsorption measurements.

In an interesting study, El-Etre investigated the stem extract of *Opuntia* (Paddle cactus, India, Mexico, North Africa and some parts in Europe) for corrosion inhibition of aluminium in HCl acid solution, in which the extract was obtained by squeezing the stem instead of extracting with some solvent, and the juice was directly applied as the inhibitor [23]. The aging effect of the inhibitor was also studied, which is discussed in the later section.

Natural oils are one of the green inhibitors from plant sources. Pennyroyal oil was extracted from *Mentha pulegium* (Pennyroyal Mint) and studied for corrosion inhibition of steel in HCl corrosive medium [24]. The major constituent of Pennyroyal oil was *R-(+)-pulegone* [25]. The inhibition efficiency of the inhibitor increased with temperature, which clearly indicated the chemisorption of the inhibitor on the surface of the steel. And the inhibitor was classified as cathodic type inhibitor.

According to Riggs [26], if the displacement of corrosion potential during electrochemical polarization of the metal is more than ± 85 mV with respect to the corrosion potential of the blank, the inhibitor can be considered as a distinctive cathodic or anodic type. Similarly, inhibition effect of Jojoba oil (*Simmondsia chinensis*, Arizona, California, Mexico) and *Artemisia oil* (Mugwort, India, Nepal, China, Korea and Japan) were studied for steel corrosion in HCl medium under different temperatures [27, 28]. Abdullah et al studied the inhibitory effect of natural clove oil for corrosion inhibition of nickel and its alloys namely, Inconel 600, and Inconel 690 in different concentrations of HCl solutions [29].

Sethuraman et al has performed a series of investigations on corrosion inhibition of mild steel in acidic medium using various plant extracts. For example, black pepper [30], *Datura metel* (Angel's trumpet, India and other tropical regions) [31], and *Strychnos nux-vomica* (Poison nut, India and South-East Asia) [32] have been studied against the corrosion of mild steel in HCl as well in H_2SO_4 .

The extract of khillah seeds (*Ammi visnaga*) was studied against the corrosion of SX 316 stainless steel in HCl solution [33]. The mechanism of inhibitive effect of the khillah seed extract was studied by comparing the complexing ability of the compounds khellin and visnagin that are major constituents of khillah seed extract. The conductometric titrations showed the possible

formation of Fe-khellin or Fe-visnagin complex, which is usually attributed to chemisorption or chemical bonding between the iron and inhibitor molecules. But in contrary to that the inhibition efficiency of the extract significantly decreased with increasing the temperature, which indicated the mechanism of adsorption of the inhibitor molecules were predominantly physisorption. Though the decrease in the inhibition efficiency was observed at elevated temperatures, the seed extract exhibited mostly 71% of inhibition efficiency for 120 ppm at 80 °C.

The anti-corrosion behavior of lupine (*Lupinus albus* L., White lupine, Egypt, Sudan, Ethiopia, Central and Western Europe) extract on the corrosion of steel in aqueous solution of H₂SO₄ and HCl was investigated by Abdel-Gaber et al [34]. The corrosion data were tested with kinetic-thermodynamic model to reveal the adsorption mechanism of inhibition. The inhibitor showed comparatively higher efficiency in HCl than in H₂SO₄.

Abiola et al described the inhibition of corrosion of aluminium in sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution using leaves and seed extract of *Gossipium hirsutum* L. (Upland Cotton) [35]. The leaf extract showed significantly higher inhibition efficiency (97%) than the seed extract (94%). In a similar manner, the extracts of *Carica papaya* leaves, seeds, heartwood, and bark were evaluated for corrosion inhibition of mild steel in H₂SO₄ acid solution [36]. The leaf extract showed an higher inhibition efficiency compared to the extracts from seed, heartwood and bark.

The *Gongronema latifolium* extract was studied for corrosion inhibition of aluminium in both acidic and basic conditions [37]. The inhibitor showed higher inhibition efficiency in HCl than in NaOH. The suggested mechanism for the predominant corrosion inhibition in HCl solution was chemisorption, whereas physisorption was attributed for the inhibitor's effectiveness against NaOH solution.

Corrosion inhibition of zinc in HCl solution was studied using *Aloe vera* (Arabian Peninsula, North Africa and other tropical regions) gel extract [38]. In this case, the gel was squeezed out from fresh leaves. The juice was appropriately diluted and then the solution was directly studied acid corrosion of zinc. The corrosion data from weight loss measurements were found to have first-order kinetics relationship.

El-Etre evaluated the inhibition potential of the aqueous extract of zallouh root for corrosion of carbon steel in HCl solution [39]. The relatively low value of activation energy in the presence of zallouh extract indicated that the mechanism of inhibition was provided by the physical adsorption of inhibitor molecules on the steel surface.

Inorganic green inhibitors

Inorganic elements or metals have a crucial role in living organisms, when they are at trace amounts. The higher concentrations of many metals cause toxicity to all forms of lives. It is also applicable for the derivatives of metals. For example, chromium compounds, mainly chromates were widely used as potential corrosion inhibitors in aqueous

systems due to their high efficiency [40-42]. Besides the high inhibition efficiency, chromates exhibit high toxicity and consequently prohibited to use for industrial applications [43]. In search of alternatives for chromate inhibitors, lanthanide salts are found to show excellent inhibition properties [44, 45]. Lanthanide salts like lanthanide chlorides were reported to possess toxicity that is comparable with sodium chloride [46]. Hence lathanide salts can also be considered as green inhibitor or eco-friendly inhibitor (Table 2).

Table 2 Inorganic-green inhibitors

Inhibitor	Metal	Medium	Ref.
CeCl ₃	AA5083, galvanized steel	NaCl	47
CeCl ₃ .7H ₂ O	Tinned iron	NaCl	48
La(NO ₃) ₃ , Sm(NO ₃) ₃ , LaCl ₃ , and SmCl ₃	AISI 434 SS	NaCl	49

A few research studies were reported on the corrosion inhibition properties of lanthanides during the last decade. For example, Arenas et al reported the application of CeCl₃ as an inhibitor for an aluminium alloy (AA5083) and galvanized steel in aerated NaCl solutions [47]. The study has provided evidence for the formation of an inhibitor layer on the surface of alloy as well on galvanized steel. The presence of Ce⁴⁺ was observed which was due to the oxidation of Ce³⁺. The phenomenon of "over precipitation" of cerium particles was observed on some areas of galvanized steel surface. This was attributed to the loss in the film coherence that occurs when it reaches critical thickness. The yellow coloration of the layer formed on the galvanized steel was not observed for the aluminium alloy, which may be due to the microscopic sizes of the precipitates.

In another attempt by Arenas et al, CeCl₃.7H₂O was employed as corrosion inhibitor for tinned iron or tin plate in NaCl solutions [48]. The coulometric studies revealed the cathodic nature of the inhibitor, which was similar to their previous report [47]. Similarly, Bernal et al reported the inhibitive effects of lanthanum nitrate (La(NO₃)₃), samarium nitrate (Sm(NO₃)₃), lanthanum chloride (LaCl₃), and samarium chloride (SmCl₃) for corrosion of AISI 434 SS in sodium chloride solutions [49]. Even though the nitrate ion is considered as an anodic inhibitor, the studied rare earth nitrates (La(NO₃)₃, Sm(NO₃)₃) were demonstrated as mixed-type inhibitors, which was attributed to the presence of lanthanide ions in the solutions. Interestingly, for rare earth chlorides decrease in inhibition efficiency was observed on increasing the inhibitor concentration. This negative effect was interpreted as due to the increase in the concentration of the chloride ions.

Natural Polymers

Polymers are the materials that have

excellent adhesive properties on metal surfaces. A wide range of polymers has been studied for their anti-corrosive properties in the form of both pre-coating [50-55] on the metal as well as inhibitor in a variety of corrosive fluids [56-63] (**Table 3**). The inhibitory mechanism of mimosa tannin against corrosion of low-carbon steel in acid solution was reported by Martinez et al [56]. The adsorption mechanism of the mimosa tannin was studied at pH 1-3. It is interesting to note that at pH 1-2 the inhibitor adopts chemisorption mechanism, where as the mechanism of inhibition switched to physisorption at pH 3.

Table 3 List of natural polymers and derivatives studied as corrosion inhibitor

Inhibitor	Metal	Medium	Ref.
Mimosa tannin	Low carbon steel	H ₂ SO ₄	56
Guar Gum	Carbon steel	H ₂ SO ₄	57
Gum Arabic	Mild steel	H ₂ SO ₄	58
Exudate Gums	Aluminium	HCl	59
Carboxymethyl cellulose	Mild steel	HCl	60
Carboxymethyl cellulose	Mild steel	H ₂ SO ₄	61, 62
Starch	Mild steel	H ₂ SO ₄	63

Guar gum, a naturally-occurring polysaccharide was examined for corrosion inhibition of carbon steel in sulfuric acid solutions [57]. An adsorption mechanism was proposed for the inhibitive nature of Guar gum. The increase in the concentration of the inhibitor had increased the resistance to pitting corrosion, which was supported by the shifts in the pitting potentials. The interaction between the oxygen atoms present on the side chains, and ferrous ions were probably impossible. Therefore, the possible mode of coordination type bonding was assumed to occur between the ferrous ions and the oxygen atoms present in the backbone of the polymer.

In an attempt to compare the inhibition efficiencies of a natural polymers and synthetic polymers, Umoren et al [58] studied gum Arabic and polyethylene glycol for corrosion inhibition of mild steel in sulphuric acid solutions. The synergistic effects of halide derivatives were also studied. The authors have also reported the inhibitive properties of exudate gum for aluminium corrosion inhibition in acidic medium [59]. Though the time dependence of the inhibition efficiencies of exudates gum followed almost similar trend to gum Arabic, the effect of temperature was different. The inhibition efficiency was increasing on temperature scale for the former, where as it was decreasing for the later. Therefore, the exudate gums was proposed to have physically adsorbed on the surface of aluminium.

Cellulose is a most abundant water-insoluble natural polysaccharide. Carboxymethyl cellulose is a water-soluble (semi-) synthetic analog of cellulose. The anti-corrosion properties of carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) were studied for mild

steel in different acid solutions [60-62]. Bayol et al have studied the adsorptive behavior of CMC on mild steel in HCl solutions [60]. Umoren et al reported the inhibition potential of CMC for sulphuric acid corrosion of mild steel [61, 62] and also the effects of synergism and antagonism of halide ions with CMC on corrosion inhibition.

Another natural polymer, starch was investigated by Mobin et al [63], for inhibition of mild steel corrosion in sulphuric acid. The synergistic effects of surfactants such as sodium dodecyl sulfate and cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide on the corrosion inhibition behavior of starch was also studied. Similar to the previous reports on the anti-corrosion properties of natural polymers as described above, the inhibition mechanism of starch was proposed as physical adsorption.

Bio-mimicking of Green Inhibitors

It is well known that green inhibitors like plant extracts contain numerous organic compounds. It is rather difficult to understand the mechanism of inhibition for a cluster of different compounds present in a plant extract. Investigation of the synthetic analogs of naturally occurring flavones, amino acids are very much dexterous to figure out the mechanisms involved in the inhibition process. For example, 3-hydroxy flavone, 2,3-dihydroxy flavanone were investigated by the authors for acid corrosion of mild steel [12, 13] (**Table 4**).

Table 4 Model green inhibitors

Inhibitor	Metal	Medium	Ref.
3-Hydroxyflavone	Mild steel	HCl	12
2,3-Dihydroxy flavanone	Mild steel	HCl	13
Methionine	Mild steel	H ₂ SO ₄	64
Tryptophan	low-carbon steel	HCl	65
Cysteine, glycine, leucine, & alanine	Mild steel	HCl	66
Cysteine	Copper	NaCl, HCl	67
Serine, threonine, & glutamic acid	Copper	HCl	68

The flavone derivatives were found to adsorb on the mild steel surface via both physical and chemical adsorptions. Similarly, amino acids alanine, cysteine, glutamic acid, glycine, leucine, serine, threonine, tryptophan were studied mainly for corrosion inhibition of steel [64-66] and also for copper corrosion [67, 68].

Oguzie et al [64] investigated the inhibition mechanisms of methionine for acid corrosion of mild steel along with synergistic effect of iodide ion. The results showed that the synergistic effect of iodide ion increased on increasing the population of specific adsorbed I⁻ ions for ion-pair formation with methionine cations. The adsorption of L-tryptophan on low-carbon steel was evaluated by Fu et al [65].

The quantum chemical calculations determined the possible adsorption centers of L-tryptophan and also its flat orientation with respect to the Fe surface. Similarly, quantitative structural activity relationship for four amino acids namely, cysteine, glycine, leucine and alanine were studied [66]. And cysteine was found to possess higher inhibition efficiency than the other studied amino acids.

Khaled et al [67] has examined cysteine for corrosion inhibition of copper. The synergistic effect of Cu^{2+} ions was investigated. At higher concentrations of Cu^{2+} ions, decrease in inhibition efficiency was reported in this study. And at very low concentrations (0.01 mM) of Cu^{2+} ions, the inhibition efficiency did not change, which may be due to the adsorbed layer formation by amino acid itself. Similarly, Zhang et al [68] examined the corrosion inhibition property of Serine, threonine and glutamic acid against copper corrosion. Glutamic acid showed higher inhibition potential due to the presence of carboxylate ions.

General Characteristics of Green Inhibitors

Green inhibitors have properties that are similar to the 'non-green' inhibitors. Most of the green inhibitors adsorb on the metal surface by means of both physical and chemical adsorption at room temperature. At elevated temperatures, inhibition occurs mainly through chemisorption. On prolonged exposure of the green inhibitor towards the corrosive environment, inhibitor gains or losses its effectiveness during the process of corrosion inhibition. The evaluation of the effect of increased time on the inhibition efficiency lends information about the stability of inhibitive behavior of the green inhibitor on time scale. In most of the cases, the effectiveness of the inhibitor decreases upon increasing the time, which means that the adsorption of the inhibitor molecules on the metal surface occurs predominantly via physical interactions [10-16, 22, 23, 58-60, 67-81].

There are few reports that show an increase of inhibition efficiency of the green inhibitor on time scale. For example, investigations on the leaf extract of *Clematis gouriana* for acid corrosion of mild steel revealed that the inhibition efficiency increases on increasing the immersion time of the steel specimen in the acid solution containing 400 ppm concentration of the inhibitor [10]. This was attributed to the stability and persistence of the adsorbed inhibitor layer on the steel surface. Singh et al [81] has reported the trend of an increase of inhibition efficiency along with time, which was also observed for a synthetic natural product 2,3-dihydroxyflavanone [11].

It is important to consider the concentration of the inhibitor to achieve maximum efficiency. Though the compositions and sources are different for the inhibitors, with respect to the reaction conditions, the inhibition efficiencies of the plant extract of *Justicia gendarussa* [21] and Pennyroyal oil from *Mentha pulegium* [24] can be compared. 93% of inhibition efficiency was achieved for 150 ppm of *Justicia gendarussa* plant extract, whereas 2.76 g/L (approximately 2760 ppm) is needed to attain 80% of inhibition efficiency for Pennyroyal oil. In such a case, consideration of the effect of synergism is

valuable. For example, Oguzie [74] reported the synergistic effect of halide derivatives on inhibition of acid corrosion of mild steel by plant extracts. The synergistic effects of KCl, KBr and KI increased the inhibition potential of 10 (v/v) % of *Occimum viridis* from 69% to 87%, 88% and 95%, respectively. While comparing the green inhibitors with non-green inhibitors, the latter show better inhibition efficiency. For example, benzimidazole and triazole derivatives are well known corrosion inhibitors that showed more than 97% of inhibition against acid corrosion of mild steel [82, 83] but they are also known for their toxicity [84, 85, 86, 87].

Though the inhibitors of biological origin are presumably eco-friendly, it is highly preferable to be familiar with the EC50 (Effective Concentration 50) and LD50 (Lethal Dose 50) for the inhibitors with irrespective of their origins. These cytotoxicity experiments can give a solid evidence for the biocompatibility of the inhibitors.

An Overview on Selectivity of Green Inhibitors

A thorough examination of the available literatures revealed that a universal eco-friendly corrosion inhibitor that is applicable to most of the metals is yet to be discovered or invented. There are few reports that compare the efficacy of the inhibitors for different metals against various corrosive environments [69-73]. Rehan has investigated the water extracts of leaves of date palm, *phoenix dactylifera*, henna, *lawsonia inermis*, and corn, *zea mays* against the acidic and basic corrosion of steel, aluminium, copper and brass [69]. The results showed that the inhibition action was purely dependant on the metal type and the composition of solution. For example, 1% solutions of henna extracts showed no inhibition for aluminium in 0.2 M hydrochloric acid solutions; whereas 86% of inhibition was observed for the corrosion of steel. Meanwhile, 96% inhibition of corrosion was observed against the alkaline corrosion of aluminium, which indicated that the inhibition efficacy of an inhibitor is greatly affected not only by the type of metal but also by the corrosive medium.

El-Etre et al reported the versatility of lawsonia extract for acidic, neutral and alkaline corrosion of C-steel, nickel and zinc [70]. For C-steel and nickel better inhibition was observed in acid solutions with the inhibitor. On the other hand, lawsonia extract potentially inhibited the corrosion of zinc in neutral solutions.

Conclusions

Generally green inhibitors are excellent inhibitors under a variety of corrosive environments for most of the metals. The non-toxicity and biodegradability are the major advantages for these inhibitors. However, they do have performance boundaries. Although a number of publications are witnessing the green inhibitors as a potential candidate against corrosion at different environments, further research efforts are needed to employ the green inhibitors widely at an industrial level.

References

1. Koch GH, Brongers MPH, Thompson NG, Virmani YP, Payer JH (2002) Corrosion costs and preventive strategies in the United States. NACE Intl PHWA-RD-01-156
2. Speller FN, Chappel EL, Russell RP (1927) Practical applications of inhibitors for pickling operations. Trans Am Inst Chem Engrs 19:165
3. Sanyal B (1981) Organic compounds as corrosion inhibitors in different environments- A review. Prog Org Coat 9:165-236
4. Raja PB, Sethuraman MG (2008) Natural products as corrosion inhibitor for metals in corrosive media-A review. Mater Letts 62:113-116
5. Amitha Rani BE, Bharathi Bai JB (2011) Green inhibitors for corrosion protection of metals and alloys-An overview. Intl J Corr DOI: 10.1155/2012/380217
6. Bethencourt M, Botana FJ, Calvino JJ, Marcos M, Rodrigues-Chacon MA (1998) Lanthanide compounds as environmentally-friendly corrosion inhibitors of aluminium alloys: A review. Corr Sci 40:1803-1819
7. Abdullah DM (2011) A review: plant extracts and oils as corrosion inhibitors in aggressive media. Indus Lub Trib 63:227-233
8. Protopopoff E, Marcus P (1995) Electrochemistry and materials science of cathodic hydrogen absorption and adsorption, PV 94-21. Conway, BE, Jerkiewicz, G, J. Electrochem Soc NJ 374-386
9. Jerkiewicz G, Borodzinski JJ, Chrzanowski W, Conway BE (1995) Examination of factors influencing promotion of H absorption into metals by site-blocking elements. J Electrochem Soc 142:3755-3763
10. Gopiraman M, Sakunthala P, Kanmani R, Alex Ramani V, Sulochana N (2011) Inhibitive action of Clematis gouriana extract on the corrosion of mild steel in acidic medium. Ionics DOI:10.1007/s11581-011-5480584-9
11. Gopiraman M, Sakunthala P, Kesavan D, Alexramani V, Kim IS, Sulochana N (2011) An Investigation of mild carbon steel corrosion inhibition in hydrochloric acid medium by environment friendly green inhibitors. J Coat Technol Res DOI 10.1007/s11998-011-9374-6
12. Lavanya MN, Kesavan D, Prabhavathi N, Sulochana N (2009) Studies on inhibitive effect of 3-hydroxyflavone on the acid corrosion of mild steel. Surf Rev Letts 16:845-853
13. Gopiraman M, Sathya C, Vivekananthan S, Kesavan D, Sulochana N (2011) Influence of 2,3-dihydroxyflavanone on corrosion inhibition of mild steel in acidic medium. J Mater Eng Perform DOI:10.1007/s11665-011-9925-0
14. Ashok Kumar S, Gopiraman M, Saravana Kumar M, Sreekanth A (2011) 2-Acetylpyridine N(4) morpholine thiosemicarbazone (HAcPMTSc) as a corrosion inhibitor on mild steel in HCl. Ind Eng Chem Res 50:7824-7832
15. Gopiraman M, Selvakumaran N, Kesavan D, Karvembu R (2012) Adsorption and corrosion inhibition behaviour of N-(phenylcarbamothioyl)benzamide on mild steel in acidic medium. Prog Org Coat 73:104-111
16. Kesavan D, Muthu Tamizh M, Gopiraman M, Sulochana N, Karvembu R (2012) Physico-chemical studies of 4-substitute N-(2-mercapto-phenyl)-salicylideneimines: Corrosion inhibition of mild steel in an acid medium. J Surfact Deterg DOI:10.1007/s11743-012-1338-z
17. Baskar R, Gopiraman M, Kesavan D, Kim IS, Subramanian K (2012) Synthesis, characterization, and electrochemical studies of novel biphenyl based compounds. Ind Eng Chem Res DOI:10.1021/ie201470j
18. Loto CA (2001) The effect of mango bark and leaf extract solution additives on the corrosion inhibition of mild steel in dilute sulphuric acid. Part 1. Corr Prev Cont 48:38-41
19. Loto CA (2001) The effect of mango bark and leaf extract solution additives on the corrosion inhibition of mild steel in dilute sulphuric acid. Part 2. Corr Prev Cont 48:59-64
20. Gunasekaran G, Chauhan LR (2004) Eco friendly inhibitor for corrosion inhibition of mild steel in phosphoric acid medium. Electrochim Acta 49:4387-4395
21. Satapathy AK, Gunasekaran G, Sahoo SC, Kumar A, Rodrigues PV (2009) Corrosion inhibition by Justicia gendarussa plant extract in hydrochloric acid solution. Corr Sci 51:2848-2856
22. Okafor PC, Ikpi ME, Uwah IE, Ebenso EE, Ekpe UJ, Umoren SA (2008) Inhibitory action of Phyllanthus amarus extracts on the corrosion of mild steel in acidic media. Corr Sci 50:2310-2317
23. El-Etre (2003) Inhibition of aluminium corrosion using Opuntia extract. Corr Sci 45:2485-2495
24. Bouyanzer A, Hammouti B, Majidi L (2006) Pennyroyal oil from Mentha pulegium as corrosion inhibitor for steel in 1 M HCl. Mater Lett 60:2840-2843
25. Majidi L, Idrissi M, Hnach M (2005) ChemInform 36:757
26. Riggs OL (1973) Corrosion inhibitors, 2nd Edition, Ed. Nathan, CC, Houston, TX, 43
27. Chetouani A, Hammouti B, Benkaddour M (2004) Corrosion inhibition of iron in hydrochloric acid solution by jojoba oil. Pigment Res Technol 33:26-31.
28. Bouyanzer A, Hammouti B (2004) A study of anti-corrosive effects of Artemisia oil on steel. Pigment Res Technol 33:287-292.
29. Abdullah M, Al Karanee SO, Abdel Fattah AA (2009) Inhibition of the corrosion of nickel and its alloys by natural clove oil. Chem Eng Commun 196:1406-1416
30. Bothi Raja P, Sethuraman MG, Inhibitive effect of black pepper extract on the sulphuric acid corrosion of mild steel. Mater Lett 62:2977-2979
31. Sethuraman MG, Bothi Raja P (2005) Corrosion inhibition of mild steel by Datura metel. Pigment Res Technol 34:327-331
32. Bothi Raja P, Sethuraman MG (2009) Strychnos nux-vomica an eco-friendly corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in 1 M sulfuric acid medium. Mater Corros 60:22-28
33. El-Etre AY (2006) Khilah extract as inhibitor for acid corrosion of SX 316 steel. Appl Surf Sci

- 252:8521-8525
34. Abdel-Gaber AM, Abd-El-Nabey BA, Saadawy M (2009) The role of acid anion on the inhibition of the acidic corrosion of steel by lupine extract. *Corr Sci* 51:1038-1042
35. Abiola OK, Otaigbe JOE, Kio OJ (2009) *Gossypium hirsutum* L. extracts as green corrosion inhibitor for aluminum in NaOH solution. *Corr Sci* 51:1879-1881
36. Okafor PC, Ebenso EE (2007) Inhibitive action of *Carica papaya* extracts on the corrosion of mild steel in acidic media and their adsorption characteristics. *Pigment Res Technol* 36:134-140
37. Oguzie EE, Onuoha GN, Ejike EE (2007) Effect of *Gongronema latifolium* extract on aluminium corrosion in acidic and alkaline media. *Pigment Res Technol* 36:44-49
38. Abiola OK, James AO (2010) The effects of Aloe vera extract on corrosion and kinetics of corrosion process of zinc in HCl solution. *Corr Sci* 52:661-664
39. El-Etre AY (2008) Inhibition of C-steel corrosion in acidic solution using the aqueous extract of zallouh root. *Mater Chem Phys* 108:278-282
40. Maji KD, Sing I, Kumar R (1976) *Trans Ind Inst Metals* 29:374
41. McCafferty E (1979) Thermodynamic aspects of the crevice corrosion of iron in chromate/chloride solutions. *J Electrochem Soc* 126:385
42. McCafferty E (1989) Thermodynamic aspects of the crevice corrosion of iron in chromate/chloride solutions. *Corros Sci* 29:391
43. U.S. Congress, Office of Technology Assessment, Environmental Policy Tools: A User's Guide, OTA-ENV-634 (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, September 1995).
44. Twite RL, Bierwagen GP (1998) Review of alternatives to chromate for corrosion protection of aluminum aerospace alloys. *Prog Org Coat* 33:91-100
45. Bethencourt M, Botana FJ, Calvino JJ, Marcos M, Rodriguez-Chacon MA (1998) Lanthanide compounds as environmentally-friendly corrosion inhibitors of aluminium alloys: A review. *Corr Sci* 40:1803-1819
46. Toxicological profile for chromium, agency for toxic substance (1989) US Public Health Service, Report, no. ATSDR/TP-88/10
47. Arenas A, Bethencourt M, Botana FJ, de Damborenea J, Marcos M (2001) Inhibition of 5083 aluminium alloy and galvanized steel by lanthanide salts. *Corr Sci* 43:157-170
48. Arenas MA, Conde A, de Damborenea JJ (2002) Cerium: a suitable green corrosion inhibitor for tinplate. *Corr Sci* 44:511-520
49. Bernal S, Botana FJ, Calvino JJ, Marcos M, Perez-Omil JA, Vidal H (1995) Lanthanide salts as alternative corrosion inhibitors. *J Alloy Comp* 255:638-641
50. Ansari R, Alikhani AH (2009) Application of polyaniline/nylon composites coating for corrosion protection of steel. *J Coat Technol Res* 6:221-227
51. Zaarei D, Sarabi AA, Sharif F, Gudarzi MM, Kassiriha SM (2011) A new approach to using submicron emeraldine-base polyaniline in corrosion-resistant epoxy coatings. *J Coat Technol Res* DOI:10.1007/s11998-011-9325-2
52. Mobin M, Tanveer N (2011) Corrosion performance of chemically synthesized poly(aniline-co-o-toluidine) copolymer coating on mild steel. *J Coat Technol Res* DOI 10.1007/s11998-011-9328-z
53. Alam J, Riaz U, Ashraf SM, Ahmad S (2008) Corrosion-protective performance of nano polyaniline/ferrite dispersed alkyd coatings. *J Coat Technol Res* 5:123-128
54. Zaarei D, Sarabi AA, Sharif F, Kassiriha SM (2008) Structure, properties and corrosion resistivity of polymeric nanocomposite coatings based on layered silicates. *J Coat Technol Res* 5:241-249
55. Jadhav RS, Hundiwale DG, Mahulikar PP (2010) Synthesis of nano polyaniline and poly-o-anisidine and applications in alkyd paint formulation to enhance the corrosion resistivity of mild steel. *J Coat Technol Res* 7:449-454
56. Martinez S, Stern I (2001) Inhibitory mechanism of low-carbon steel corrosion by mimosa tannin in sulphuric acid solutions. *J Appl Electrochemistry* 31:973-978
57. Abdallah M (2004) Guar gum as corrosion inhibitor for carbon steel in sulfuric acid solutions. *Port Electrochim Acta* 22:161-175
58. Umoren SA, Ogbobe O, Igwe IO, Ebenso EE (2008) Inhibition of mild steel corrosion in acidic medium using synthetic and naturally occurring polymers and synergistic halide additives. *Corr Sci* 50:1998-2006
59. Umoren SA, Obot IB, Ebenso EE, Okafor PC (2008) Eco-friendly Inhibitors from Naturally occurring exudate gums for aluminium corrosion inhibition in acidic medium. *Port Electrochim Acta* 26:267-282
60. Bayol E, Gürten AA, Dursun M, Kayakirilmaz K (2008) Adsorption behavior and inhibition corrosion effect of sodium carboxymethyl cellulose on mild steel in acidic medium. *Acta Physico-Chimica Sinica* 24:2236-2243
61. Solomon MM, Umoren SA, Udosoro II, Udoh AP (2010) Inhibitive and adsorption behaviour of carboxymethyl cellulose on mild steel corrosion in sulphuric acid solution. *Corr Sci* 52:1317-1325
62. Umoren SA, Solomon MM, Udosoro II, Udoh AP (2010) Synergistic and antagonistic effects between halide ions and carboxymethyl cellulose for the corrosion inhibition of mild steel in sulphuric acid solution. *Cellulose* 17:635-648
63. Mobin M, Khan MA, Parveen M (2011) Inhibition of mild steel corrosion in acidic medium using starch and surfactants additives. *J Appl Poly Sci* 121:1558-1565
64. Oguzie EE, Li Y, Wang FH (2007) Corrosion inhibition and adsorption behavior of methionine on mild steel in sulfuric acid and synergistic effect of iodide ion. *J Colloid Interface Sci* 310:90-98
65. Fu JJ, Li SN, Cao LH, Wang Y, Yan LH, Lu LD (2010) L-Tryptophan as green corrosion inhibitor for low carbon steel in hydrochloric acid solution. *J Mater Sci* 45:979-986
66. Eddy NO, Awel FE, Gimbal CE, Ibisi NO, Ebenso EE (2011) QSAR, experimental and computational chemistry simulation studies on the inhibition

- potentials of some amino acids for the corrosion of mild steel in 0.1 M HCl. *Int J Electrochem Sci* 6:931-957
67. Ismail KM (2007) Evaluation of cysteine as environmentally friendly corrosion inhibitor for copper in neutral and acidic chloride solutions. *Electrochimica Acta* 52:7811-7819
68. Zhang DQ, Cai QR, Gao LX, Lee KY (2008) Effect of serine, threonine and glutamic acid on the corrosion of copper in aerated hydrochloric acid solution. *Corr Sci* 50:3615-3621
69. Rehan HH (2003) Corrosion control by water-soluble extracts from leaves of economic plants. *Mat wiss U Werkstofftech* 34:232-237
70. El-Etre AY, Abdallah M, El-Tantawy ZE (2005) Corrosion inhibition of some metals using lawsonia extract. *Corr Sci* 47:385-395
71. Poongothai N, Rajendran N, Palaniswamy M (2005) Wood bark oils as vapour phase corrosion inhibitors for metals in NaCl and SO₂ environments. *Indian J Chem Technol* 12:641-647
72. Oguzie EE (2007) Corrosion inhibition of aluminium in acidic and alkaline media by *Sansevieria trifasciata* extract. *Corr Sci* 49:1527-1539
73. Avwiri GO, Igbo FO (2003) Inhibitive action of *Vernonia amygdalina* on the corrosion of aluminium alloys in acidic media. *Mater Lett* 57:3705-3711
74. Oguzie EE (2008) Evaluation of the inhibitive effect of some plant extracts on the acid corrosion of mild steel. *Corr Sci* 50:2993-2998
75. Moretti G, Guidi F, Grion G (2004) Tryptamine as a green iron corrosion inhibition in 0.5 M deaerated sulphuric acid. *Corr Sci* 46:387-403
76. James AO, Akarantha O (2011) Inhibition of corrosion of zinc in hydrochloric acid solution by red onion skin acetone extract. *Res J Chem Sci* 1:31-37
77. Ismail M, Abdulrahman AS, Hussain MS (2011) Solid waste as environmental benign corrosion inhibitors in acid medium. *Int J Eng Sci Tech* 3:1742-1748
78. Orubite KO, Oforka NC (2008) Inhibition of the corrosion of mild steel in hydrochloric acid solutions by the extracts of leaves of *Nypa fruticans* Wurmb. *Mater Lett* 58:1768-1772
79. Oguzie EE (2006) Studies on the inhibitive effect of *Occimum viridis* extract on the acid corrosion of mild steel. *Mater Chem Phys* 99:441-446
80. Obot IB, Obi-Egbedi NO, Umoren SA, Ebenso EE (2010) Synergistic and antagonistic effects of anions and *Ipomoea involvata* as green corrosion inhibitor for aluminium dissolution in acidic medium. *Int J Electrochem Sci* 5 994-1007
81. Singh A, Ahamad I, Singh VK, Quraishi MA (2010) Inhibition effect of environmentally benign karanj (*Pongamia pinnata*) seed extract on corrosion of mild steel in hydrochloric acid solution. *J Solid State Electrochem* 15:1087-1097
82. Lagrenée M, Mernari, B, Bouanis M, Traisnel M, Bentiss F (2002) Study of the mechanism and inhibiting efficiency of 3,5-bis(4-methylthio-phenyl)-4H-1,2,4- triazole on mild steel corrosion in acidic media. *Corros Sci* 44:573-588
83. Popova A, Sokolova E, Raicheva S, Christov M (2003) AC and DC study of the temperature effect on mild steel corrosion in acid media in the presence of benzimidazole derivatives. *Corros Sci* 45:33-35
84. Su JO, Jeongim P, Min JL, So YP, Kyungho C (2006) Ecological hazard assessment of major veterinary benzimidazoles: Acute and chronic toxicities to aquatic microbes and invertebrates. *Env Tox Chem* 25:2221-2226
85. Minling G, Wenhua S, Xiaoying C (2010) The acute toxicity of triazoles to earthworms using a simple paper contact method. 4th Intl. Conf. Bioinform. Biomed. Engg DOI 10.1109/ICBBE.2010.5515198
86. Martin MT, Brennan RJ, Hu W, Ayanoglu E, Lau C, Ren H, Wood CR, Corton JC, Kavlock RJ, Dix DJ (2007) Toxicogenomic study of triazole fungicides and perfluoroalkyl acids in rat livers predicts toxicity and categorizes chemicals based on mechanism of toxicity. *Toxicol Sci* 97:595-613
87. 1,2,4-triazole – Identification, toxicity, use, water pollution potential, ecological toxicity and regulatory information, <http://www.pesticideinfo.org>

© 2012, by the Authors. The articles published from this journal are distributed to the public under “Creative Commons Attribution License” (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>).

Therefore, upon proper citation of the original work, all the articles can be used without any restriction or can be distributed in any medium in any form.

Received : 01st May, 2012

Revised : 17th May, 2012

Online : 19th May, 2012